

Performance Analysis of an Underwater Acoustic Communication System Based on DCSK Modulation

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Abstract— In this paper, a communication system based on DCSK - Differential chaotic shift keying modulation, which can be used in underwater acoustic communications, is proposed. Recently, we see an increase of various communication schemes using chaotic signals, which show good results in terms of signal propagation in dense environments. In this paper, three chaotic systems have been used and compared: Logistic map, Henon map and Tent map.

The influence of the seawater on the propagation of acoustic signals is analyzed in such a way that instead of white Gaussian noise, a real recording in .wav format, made in the North Sea, was used in the simulations. Simulations and modeling of the communication system were performed in MATLAB.

I. INTRODUCTION

Underwater acoustic communications are the most common type of underwater communications. With the enormous increase in underwater sensors, especially in the IoT concept, underwater acoustic communications are becoming a fast-growing field with increasing application in the monitoring of various parameters that affect the underwater ecosystem. Among other things, acoustic communications are used for remote control during oil pollution monitoring, for collection of scientific data from ocean bottom stations, defense etc. [1]. Optical communications are impeded by water turbidity and have impact on underwater life, while electromagnetic communications have issues with high attenuation. Taking that into account, acoustic communications prove to be optimal.

On the other hand, acoustic communications are complex due to the constant movement of the transmission medium, i.e. seawater and high Doppler shift [2]. The underwater acoustic channel is non-stationery and time-dependent, which makes it difficult to model the communication channel and

design the link. In order to establish a successful communication, it is necessary to have a good knowledge of the underwater channel and the effects that appear in it. On the other hand, there is a need in designing a communication system that will work in all circumstances. Problems in acoustic communications are as follows: large number of received signals due to reflection, inter-symbol interference, movement of the water surface, large delays and large Doppler shift, variability in time as a result of sea currents, salinity, tides etc. [1].

Therefore, it is necessary to constantly research new ways of modulation that would be resistant to all these influences. To solve these problems, spread-spectrum communications are used because they can overcome channel constraints. Chaos-based communications are useful in such cases and achieve good results, they have improved security, anti-jamming and resistance to multipath fading [3].

On the other hand, the impact of acoustic communication on underwater life should be taken into account. Unlike other types of modulation, chaotic signals have a noise-similar spectrum, and thus their impact on the living world is reduced. The DCSK modulation-based chaotic communication system, as seen in this paper, is highly resistant to high noise levels that are typical for underwater communications.

II. CHAOS THEORY

Chaos is a form of steady state that, under certain conditions, manifests in many natural and man-made systems. Chaotic behavior is described in [4][5] [6] [7]. Time waveforms of a chaotic signal are qualitatively different from periodic waveforms. They appear quite irregularly; no repetition occurs in any time period of finite length. Although obtained in deterministic systems, the solutions appear to be random. Namely, in the spectrum of a periodic signal, only lines corresponding to certain frequencies can be seen, while in the spectrum of chaos, a wide flat continuum prevails. Chaotic signals have noise similar spectra.

Chaotic signals are broadband, aperiodic, and very sensitive to initial conditions [8]. It is shown that nonlinear functions can represent chaotic systems (maps) that will behave chaotically. Chaotic maps are used in many

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applications that require their pseudo-random properties and they can be in a discrete or continuous time domain. In this work, three maps were used for chaotic modulation: Logistic, Henon and Tent maps.

A. Logistic map

The logistic map shows how complex, chaotic behavior can be produced from a simple nonlinear dynamic system. The Logistic map is described by the following equation:

$$x_{n+1} = rx_n(1 - x_n) \quad (1)$$

where x_n : $[0, 1]$ represents the current state of the dynamic system, and r : $[0, 4]$ is the control parameter. For more details, see [7].

B. Henon map

Henon maps takes one point and map it to new point by relations:

$$x_{n+1} = 1 - \alpha x_n^2 + y_n \quad (2)$$

$$y_{n+1} = \beta x_n \quad (3)$$

C. Tent map

A piecewise linear, one-dimensional map on the interval $[0,1]$ exhibiting chaotic dynamics and given by

$$x_{n+1} = \mu \left(1 - 2 \left| x_n - \frac{1}{2} \right| \right) \quad (4)$$

Tent map has this name because its graphic is shaped like a tent.

III. DIFFERENTIAL CHAOTIC SHIFT KEYING (DCSK)

DCSK - Differential chaotic shift keying modulation is a chaos-based non-coherent modulation [9]. The advantage of this modulation, especially in underwater communications, is its insensitivity to frequency selective channels. For this modulation, modulator and demodulator synchronization is not required and sampling of the frame or symbol is sufficient [10]. The block diagram of the modulator is shown in Figure 1. The reference signal is sent in the first half of the symbol period, and the signal carrying the message in the second half [7].

Figure 1. Block diagram of DCSK system modulator

If “+1” is to be sent, the signal carrying the data will be identical to the reference signal and this is represented by formula [7]:

$$s(t) = \begin{cases} c(t) & \text{for } 0 \leq t < T_b / 2 \\ c(t - \frac{T_b}{2}) & \text{for } T_b / 2 \leq t < T_b \end{cases} \quad (5)$$

If “-1” is to be sent, the inverted version of the reference signal will be used as the data carrying signal.

The DCSK demodulator is shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Block diagram of DCSK system demodulator

During demodulation, the signal is correlated with the same signal but only delayed by half a period, which is actually a correlation of the reference signal and the signal that carries the data. After the correlator, a decision is made and all values that exceed zero are set to “1” and the rest are set to “0”.

In this way, half of the transmission time is spent on transmitting the reference signal, which cuts the transmission speed in half. This is one of the disadvantages of the DCSK system.

IV. UNDERWATER CHANNEL MODELING

There are a large number of models that model various parameters of the underwater acoustic channel. In paper [1] a comparative overview of these models is presented. On the other hand, some researchers use channel models that have been measured. In other words, the channel was recorded using a hydrophone and saved as a .wav file. One such example is the Watermark project [11].

In this paper, this model type was used for channel modeling.

V. SIMULATION RESULTS

In order to check the possibility of using chaotic modulations in underwater acoustic communications, a simulation of the DCSK system was made in MATLAB. The aim of the simulations is to determine the Bit Error Rate and the robustness of the acoustic signal when propagating through seawater. In the simulations, modulation was performed with three chaotic systems: Logistic map, Henon map and Tent map.

Figure 4 shows the chaotic signal obtained using the Logistic map when the parameter $r=0.8$. This signal is used to modulate the message shown in Figure 3.

The signal modulated by DCSK modulation is shown in Figure 5. As shown here, this signal is quite masked and, therefore, the safety is increased, and the spectrum of this signal is wide-band. On the other hand, it can be seen that the signal is similar to a noise, which has less influence on the underwater life than other modulation techniques.

Figure 3. Waveform of transmitted signal

Figure 4. Chaotic signal based on Logistic map

Figure 5. DCSK signal waveform modulated with Logistic map

Figure 6 shows the noise present in the underwater acoustic channel. This noise is obtained from a real recording in .wav format.

Figure 6. Noise in underwater acoustic channel

The signal that arrives at the receiver, in this case the hydrophone, is shown in Figure 7. It can be seen that the signal has a multiple times higher amplitude and a completely different waveform. This does not happen in the case of electromagnetic communications, but in the underwater environment there are many sources of sound, such as animals, ships, etc.

Figure 7. Received signal at the input of demodulator

Figure 8. Waveform of the recovered data

The demodulated signal is shown in Figure 8. It can be seen that the signal is demodulated correctly.

It can be clearly seen that the demodulation is extremely good. Figure 9 shows the BER.

Figure 9. BER plot for modulation with Logistic map

Based on the results shown in Figures 3-9, the success of this system and the justification of using chaos for modulation, can be seen.

In order to compare and analyze performance, in addition to the Logistic map, Henon and Tent maps were also implemented. The waveform of the signal at the output of the modulator when a chaotic signal was used, obtained by Henon map when parameters $\alpha=1.4$ and $\beta=0.3$, is shown in Figure 10.

Figure 10. DCSK signal waveform modulated with Henon map

The chaotic signal generated by the Tent map is shown in Figure 11. The parameter μ in this case is $\mu=0.8$.

Figure 11. DCSK signal waveform modulated with Tent map

Figure 12. BER comparison of DCSK system between Logistic, Henon and Tent map modulation

A comparative view of the BER for all three chaotic signals is shown in the figure 14.

Based on the results shown in the previous figures, it can be seen that all three chaotic signals are very different in their waveform, but that all signals are successfully demodulated even in the presence of large noise in the underwater acoustic channel.

VI. CONCLUSION

This paper presents the implementation of the DCSK communication system that can be used in underwater acoustic communications. In order to compare the performance, a system was implemented using three chaotic signals generated by Logistic, Henon and Tent maps. In addition to various models that could be used to model the channel, in this case an audio recording of the channel in real conditions was chosen, in order to model the real case as much as possible.

Based on the results presented in the paper, it can be seen that this type of modulation achieves good results and that it can be used in a very noisy underwater environment.

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